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EPISTEMOLOGI PEMERINTAHAN

Paradigma Manajemen, Birokrasi, Dan Pemerintahan

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INTRODUCTION

The author describe the process of forming the early government by offering a comparison of the ontology, epistemology and axiology of the science of government. Ontology discusses "what" what is called the Science of Government, epistemology discusses "how" how a government works, and axiology discusses "why" why a government activity is needed and realized. The extent to which the Science of Government can formulate the philosophical essence of the management of power in the structure of the problems it raises. Government science needs to be regulated in regulations that bind statutory provisions. The system relation between Government postulates as an institutionalized system requires political legitimacy that is born through the need to address public service problems. In the whole discusses several topics namely: Government Studies, Bureaucracy, Public Policy, State Civil Apparatus. In the midst of the dynamics and demands of government management, the presence in front of the readers can be the best recipe in resolving various problems that arise in the performance of government bureaucratic services.

This book is intended for students, lecturers, practitioners, state civil servants and officials, they are expected to have this book as a supporting reference in various policies and government studies that have been involved so far. In the midst of the dynamics and demands of government management, the presence in front of the readers can be the best recipe in solving various problems that arise in the performance of government bureaucratic services, more aimed at the government because the author wants a change in the issues discussed.

A good bureaucratic system is characterized by an State Civil Apparatus management organization that realizes fair and competitive selection and promotion, the fact shows that there are still many regional heads who act unfairly in promoting honestly and fairly. In addition, the low State Civil

Apparatus allowance is still not directly proportional to the regional surplus or the performance burden that state civil apparatus has been carrying in public services so far. Even the low income guarantee of state civil apparatus will affect the implementation of performance-based reward and punishment. The level of quality of public services is influenced by the ability of the merit system government in reward and punishment. This will measure the integrity of state civil apparatus in behaving as servants of the public interest. The existence of state civil apparatus is not the only determining factor for the success of performance in accelerating national development. However, as a component of government, it can be factually ascertained that the state needs state civil apparatus in carrying out public service tasks, government tasks, and certain development tasks. In summary, it actually emphasizes government functions that manage the implementation of certain development tasks carried out through nation building (cultural and political development) and economic and social development for the welfare and prosperity of the community.

The book actually emphasizes government functions that manage the implementation of certain development tasks carried out through nation-building and economic and social development for the welfare and prosperity of society. The importance of reviewing this book is to find out whether all of this has been applied correctly. It is realized that the tasks of public services, government tasks, and certain development tasks have not been fully realized due to the low level of state civil apparatus management, if reader want to get more information about the conditions of the Indonesian government regarding public services and to be able to overcome them, it is necessary to do this review first because of the complete theory studies and data presented.

RESULT

This book really meets the needs of the intended readers because it contains points that have been concluded by the author and presented in full which will be analyzed further so that readers can understand more deeply about the Science of Government, management of power, and to find out whether it has been effective and efficient regarding the application of the law. Readers will get the understandings needed for their needs, as well as what important points can be taken to meet the needs of readers. The complete content of the book will make it easier for the readers to understand clearly and concretely the parts of the book.

A good bureaucratic system is marked by the State Civil Apparatus management organization that embodies fair and competitive selection and promotion, the fact shows that there are still many regional heads who act unfairly in promoting honestly and fairly. In addition, the low State Civil Apparatus allowance is still not directly proportional to the regional surplus and the performance burden that State

Civil Apparatus has been carrying in public services so far. Even the State Civil Apparatus income guarantee will affect the implementation of performance-based reward and punishment. The level of quality of public services is influenced by the ability of the merit system government in reward and punishment. This will measure the integrity of State Civil Apparatus in behaving as servants of the public interest.

The readers becomes aware of the current state of development of the Indonesian state, and the reader becomes aware of the reasons why public services in Indonesia are not good. With this book, it can become one of the supporting references in the study of government and various policies that have been carried out so far, readers can also be bolder to express if they see deficiencies in government management, especially regarding public services by State Civil Apparatus

Evidence is supported about the government apparatus during the New Order era, the function of implementing policies, development and public services is more oriented towards the interests of groups or groups, ethnicities and religions so that they are not optimally oriented towards the interests of the community. Likewise with the journey of the Reformation Order, the roles and functions where the profile of the government bureaucracy is still marked and the development of the abuse of authority in the form of corruption, collusion and nevetism in both the central and regional governments is a sign of the condition of government bureaucratic disease in the government apparatus.

The evidence is strong because we know for ourselves how the conditions of government were during the New Order era and during the reformation era, then the author is strengthened by the opinion of two articles that discuss the lack of good management and government services in Indonesia. Then there are facts which show that there are still many regional heads who are unfair in promoting honestly and fairly. In addition, the low State Civil Apparatus allowance is still not directly proportional to the regional surplus and the performance burden that State Civil Apparatus has been carrying in public services so far. Even the low State Civil Apparatus income guarantee will affect the implementation of performance-based reward and punishment.

Evidence about the lack of good governance is evidenced in the opinion according to F.W Riggs in Pamudji (1992) that the government bureaucracy in Indonesia tends to be paternalistic, formalistic, overlapping, nepotic and mechanistic which is oriented towards status, static and mechanistic structures, mental attitudes, lack of professionalism and proliferation which is characterized by a paternalistic culture, so that it tends to hinder public services. Then the evidence of the bad government bureaucratic apparatus in Indonesia cites an article written by Abdullah (Pages 222-223).

This book is very long, so the author uses a writing style that is easy for readers to understand. The book organization has an integration between the sub-subjects by showing the problems, current conditions, and meanings of the studies discussed, as well as the size of the book that supports the author's goals. Then in each sub-subject, it cannot be separated from the theory of study which is obtained from various references concerning the topic of discussion.

The author does not ignore the study, does not ignore the facts, does not ignore the basic theory of the study that can be considered by the reader. The author has completed the objectives which are supported by facts and study theory which are described in many sub-chapters of the discussion, the sub-discussion discusses details about government regulations, laws, provisions, and the completion of these objectives can be seen in each sub-chapter in This subsection contains plans, intentions, goals, regulations so that government management can be even better.

The strength of this book is that it is very comprehensive in its reference sources. In addition to using references from various articles, and also uses the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 5 of 2004 concerning the state civil apparatus. This book can help students, lecturers, practitioners, State Civil Apparatus and officials as one of the supporting references in various government policies and studies that have been carried out so far, because has a complete discussion study.

The weakness is that the introduction does not explain what year the problem was discussed, the reader will be more interested if the first page of the book contains the year regarding the problem. Then there are still many typographical errors, such as wrong letters or missing letters in a sentence. The author should also pay more attention to PUEBI (The Indonesian Spelling System) about italics, many foreign words are not italicized.

Books are good because every discussion is accompanied by evidence. I recommend to be read because the contents of the book are quite interesting and provide insight into how the condition of the Indonesian government, both past and present, especially regarding government services to the people, my advice in writing the book should be more attention to the writing of the letters so that typographical errors and pay more attention to writing, especially slashes, must comply with the provisions of PUEBI (The Indonesian Spelling System).

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AUTHOR SHORT BIODATA

Dr. Abdul Halil Hi. Ibrahim, M.Si Born in Tobelo, August 10, 1972, Completed his undergraduate education at IAIN "Alauddin" Ujung Pandang in Ternate (1996), Masters degree in Government Science at Satyagama University Jakarta (2002) and obtained a Doctorate degree (Dr) in Government Science at Satyagama University Jakarta (2017). Devoting himself to Muhammadiyah Charities, namely as a Lecturer at the Government Science Study Program, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences (FISIP) at the Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku (UMMU) Ternate since 2002 until now, as a Postgraduate Lecturer at UMMU. The positions that have been held: Chair of the Political Science Study Program, Chair of the Government Science Study Program, Dean of FISIP UMMU (2006-2010), Chair of the UMMU FISIP Quality Assurance and now entrusted as Director of Postgraduate (s2) Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku. Director of the Study Center Regional Government (PSPD) FISIP UMMU, Married to Rusmiyanti Masuku and blessed with four children.

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born in Cirebon July 1953, studied S1 Fisip, Padjadjaran University, Bandung and S2 Fisip, Gadjah Mada University, Yogyakarta in the field of State Administration in 1978 and 1983, obtained a Doctor of Social Sciences concentration in Social Science Education (PIPS) at the University of Education Indonesia Bandung in 1996 Participated in various official course programs at home and abroad, such as Regional Development Planning in Postgraduate UI in 1985 and Comparative Local Government in Japan through JICA in 2001. Teaching experience of IIP Ministry of Home Affairs 1997-1990, STIA LAN Jakarta and Bandung 1983-2003, STPDN Jatinangor 1990 until now, Unjani 1998 until now, Satyagama University 2000 until now, Garut University 1998 until now, STIAMI Jakarta 2002 until now. Work history as Secretary of Research Center for IIP 1985, Head of Development Planning Department IIP 1987, Head of Research and Development Development IIP 1988, Assistant Chairperson of STPDN / Senate Secretary 1995, PLH Chair of STPDN 1998, Head of Training STPDN 2000, Head of Research and Development Center for Research and Development of Balitbang DDN 2001, Director of Regional Business Directorate General Bangda 2002, Director of 7 LH Spatial Planning Facilitation of the Directorate General of Bina Bangda 2004, Director of the IIP Postgraduate Program, Chair of STIP-AN for the 2014-2018 Period, He also actively participates in national seminars, workshops and symposiums at home and abroad, both

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